

A STUDY ON STRESS MANAGEMENT OF EMPLOYEES AT ITES (BPO) COMPANIES IN INDIA**Mr. Ravi Anant Jagtap***Assistant Professor,**D.V.S College of Commerce, University of Mumbai , Navi Mumbai 400701***Abstract:**

Stress is an ineluctable part of a human's life. Every employees at all levels have stress. It depending upon various factors. This research deals with the causes and remedies and strategies to be adopted to avoid or reduce work-stress. Stress can be defined as any form of happening that causes physical, emotional, or psychological deformation. . Stress is a feeling of fear, discomfort, and unease. It can be reaction to stress. The reasons maybe due to frequent changes in duty, low status in society, role conflict, increasing expectations from higher authority, irrational complaints of some self-centered customer etc. This study focuses upon the causes of this stress situation in Information Technology Enabled Services (ITES) and to suggest some meaningful solution to reduce this problem. Secondary data been use for carrying out this study. Through this researcher tries to find out the causes of these stresses among employees. Necessary suggestions are also incorporated in this research work in order to avoid such avoidable stress and to maintain a work-life balance.

Key words: *Psychological, Stress, ITES (BPOs), Self-centered*

Introduction

Stress is the being people respond physically and mentally to particular situations ,events,and that brings changes in their lives.In fact, people at all levels and positions, industries, culture, countries, get stress. It has been observed that even school and college students also have stress related to their studies, due to various reasons. Here, our focus and study is related to employees working in ITES (BPO) companies. As far as ITES (BPO) company employees are concerned, to satisfy their increasing requirements with varying expectations, it becomes a difficult task for them to meet those expectations. Apart from these expectations, other factors such as management's higher expectations from employees, pressure, policies of the management. Also external factors such as rules of RBI; government policies etc. may also lead to stress. It is necessary that one has to deal with these stresses effectively in order to maintain work-life balance and for being happy in life.It is also essential to ensure that proper rules and regulations are made and proper systems are also conducted and employees are managed well for achieving the objectives of the companies.

Need for the Study:

Although a lot of research work is being done in the field of stress effects in general, there are few studies focusing on the effects and remedial measures, especially in the field of BPO. Most focus solely on causes effects and remedial measures with business stress. The above reasons have led to the need for a comprehensive study on occupational stress in the BPO sector, including the main causes, its consequences and remedial measures that have not yet been tried by previous researchers. Apart from all these reasons, there has been no major study on the

business tensions currently operating in the BPO sector.

Objectives

To find out the causes of stress of BPO employees.

To find out the effects of these stress on Employees health

To suggest some remedial measures to solve these problems

Research Methodology

The literature review has indicated sufficient sources and theory in understanding the current scenario of Stress Management of Employees at ITES (BPO) Companies in India. The present study is based on secondary data obtained from journals, Magazines, Books and the internet website to find relevant information.

Review of Literature

BPO Employee Poll Survey (2009) conducted by (Community Portal for Outsourcing / BPO Professionals) found that middle level officers are currently under more stress than others and do not mind doing so. Switch jobs to lesser famed brands if you are offered a profitable deal.

Ramanathan S. and Sugumar D. (2013) in their research study titled “work related stressor: An Empirical study with reference to employees working in knowledge process outsourcing in Chennai, Tamil Nadu, India “Research studies have shown that these are basically middle-aged employees who register with much higher stress than older employees. The research study concluded that further research is needed to find out the major mechanisms of change in employee behavior.

In a study by Dr.Sumathi et al (2013), researchers observed that Task strategies are the most preferred for managing their stress. This means that respondents are reorganizing their tasks and organizational processes in which they are engaged in coping with stress, and fewer respondents use logic as coping strategy. And the researchers found that employees over the age of 25 are more certain and stronger than the younger age group.

Sonal Bhargava (2014) in the research study titled “Stress problem in BPO sector” It has been found that long working hours in unusual hour shifts can seriously affect the physical and mental health of workers. This study reveal that depression is a major problem facing BPO employees. Further the study have some suggestions such as organizing seminars and workshops followed by proper counseling and training for employees, organizing short trips, tie-ups with various health clubs, etc. can definitely help employees overcome adverse health effects

Sameera, Shakir Shaik and Firoz C. (2016) in their research study titled, “A Study on Stress Management among the BPO Employees in Chennai City”

One of the main findings of the study is that the majority of employees in the BPO sector experience severe stress. The researchers also demonstrated that most employees in the BPO sector do their best to find solutions to the adverse effects of stress. This study further suggests that decentralization of work is urgently needed. Researchers concluded that a conducive environment should be created for employees so that they can cope with stress in the organization

Causes of stress in BPOs

The causes of stress among BPO employees are as follows:

Work Schedule

BPO employees usually work in rotational shifts. This affects the balance of their physical health. Not everyone’s physical health will adjust to the rotational shift system.

Heavy work load

Work stress is another cause of stress. At the end of the day, the results of each employee's work should be shown. Sometimes they fail to achieve this goal and have to listen to rude language and insults from their high ranked officers

Long working hours

Employees have to work long hours due to work stress. This makes them physically and mentally weak
Insufficient leave

With the exception of statutory leave, employees do not get adequate leave to relax and spend time with their family members.

Long and unhealthy travel time

People use to go long and unhealthy travelling. They usually calculate the working hours only. Actually every day they have suicide experience while in the travel time. Long and regular travel also affects the health, due to Indian poor road conditions of many cities.

Health Problems

Rotational shifts, long journeys, Boring, improper diet, all these factors affect the health of BOP employees.

Repetition of work

BPO is not intellectual work. It calls various customers around the world. The work is very repetitive and boring in nature.

Working Condition

Many of BPO's Center do not have proper working condition.

Effects of Stress on employees may include:**Physical (Bodily)**

- Sleep disturbances
- Headaches
- Raised blood pressure/cardiovascular disease

Emotional

- Anxiety and irritability
- Depression

Intellectual (Intelligence)

- Loss of concentration
- Lack of motivation
- Poor decision-making

Behavioural (Activity)

Substance (including alcohol) misuse

Inappropriate display of behaviour

Isolation

UnPunctuality

Effects of Stress on the organization may include:

High absenteeism

High labour turnover
Poor performance and productivity
Low morale
Poor motivation
Increased employee complaints
Increased ill-health, accidents and incidents reports

Suggestions

1. Try to avoid unnecessary long working hours.it should be within statutory limits
2. In the case heavy workload,proper replacement should be done.
3. As far employees concern , for work rotation care should be taken by management to take employees into confidence in such activities .Encourage job rotation
4. Management should not give unreasonable work-stress. They should allocate work properly and employ sufficient number of staff as per the workload.
5. Employees should have reasonable freedom or independence regarding their work.
6. Time management should be adhered to.
7. Employees should be given feed-back regarding performance
8. Be always optimistic and make them optimistic.

Conclusion

Many employees have bad habits like smoking, drinking, gambling etc. Twenty-four hour duty, consumption of junk food; Night work, etc., all adversely affect the lives of BPO employees. Sexual harassment is another issue that plagues many female employees in BPOs.It is true that the employees working in BPO have a lot of depression, anxiety and stress. But if management studies the issues related to mental stress and work and addresses these issues properly as a true leader, these problems can be reduced. Unfortunately, there is not enough investigation or concern from the authorities to resolve these issues.

HR heads should take the initiative to address these issues. These workers are generally unorganized and do not have the support of trade unions. The government should give due consideration to alleviate the problems of BPO employees in India. There is scope for researchers to do more research on this topic.

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